

IHI Project ID - SYNTHIA

Synthetic Data Generation
Framework for Integrated
Validation

WP10 – Communication,
Dissemination, Training and
Policy

D10.2

Project identity and website

Lead contributor	06_MATICAL
Other contributors	01_IISLAFE

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	20/02/2025	1 st version for review
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1 Introduction

For the IHI SYNTHIA project, the communication strategy focuses on positioning SYNTHIA as a benchmark synthetic data platform in European biomedical research. It aims to build a strong ecosystem that fosters collaboration and innovation while ensuring the project delivers lasting impact through effective outreach and stakeholder engagement. In all communication activities the following objectives will be taken into account:

- **Build awareness and interest:** Effectively communicate SYNTHIA's goals and its mission to advance synthetic data generation, emphasizing its potential to transform personalized medicine. Highlight the innovative, validated tools and methods for synthetic data generation (SDG) that SYNTHIA will develop, underscoring their relevance and impact for a broad audience.
- **Drive Engagement:** Contribute to the cohesion of public and private entities, sharing insights, good practices and evidence of the value from Synthetic Data. Establish and nurture relationships with key stakeholders (HTA, regulators, public health agencies, patient associations and policymakers) for advancement on the appropriate use of Synthetic Data and acceptability in evidence-based decision-making.
- **Highlight impact:** Illustrate SYNTHIA's significance by explaining the challenges it addresses, the methodologies it uses, and the advancements it seeks to bring to research and innovation. Showcase how SYNTHIA's synthetic data approach can accelerate research, improve data accessibility, and enable more efficient and ethical innovations across healthcare and life sciences and in particular for the 6 defined use cases.
- **Disseminate knowledge and results:** Actively share SYNTHIA's findings, methodologies, and project results. Facilitate knowledge transfer to maximize the project's reach, impact, and potential for applications. Ensure a wide outreach of the project outcomes.
- **Promote transparency:** Ensure SYNTHIA's processes, findings, and outcomes are communicated openly and accessibly. Provide clear, understandable updates to build trust and maintain credibility among all stakeholders.

These above mentioned objectives will provide direction and purpose for the website design, content, functionality and maintenance.

2 The project identity

To ensure the SYNTHIA project's objectives and progress are easily recognizable to a broad professional audience and to patient communities, visually engaging materials will be developed. These materials will not only generate interest in the project, its team, and its outcomes but also support the building and maintenance of a connected and engaged stakeholder community. Tailored content will be crafted to meet the needs of different audiences, fostering ongoing engagement. Additionally, insights drawn from project deliverables, partner interviews, expert perspectives, and case studies will be shared through SYNTHIA's communication channels to deepen interaction and interest.

The IHI SYNTHIA project identity embodies pioneering, collaboration, and a commitment. While designing the identity the communication team aimed at creating a solid visual to convey progress, clarity and trust. SYNTHIA's branding symbolizes its position in the life sciences and health data arena, as well as its role to unite the public and private partners. The SYNTHIA identity is not only a representation of the project's goals and ambitions but also an invitation for stakeholders to join the SYNTHIA network in leveraging synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights

Consistency in using a corporate identity is essential not only for external engagement and dissemination, but also for internal communications. A unified corporate identity, including logo, colour schemes, typography, and messaging, ensures that SYNTHIA presents a cohesive and professional image to the outside world. Internally, consistent use of corporate identity fosters a sense of unity and belonging among the partners and collaborators. Whether communicating with external audiences or within the consortium, maintaining consistency in the SYNTHIA corporate identity will continuously strengthen the brand.

2.1 The SYNTHIA logo

- in its full form: acronym, full name and icon

- in shortened form: acronym and icon

- only the icon:

2.2 The SYNTHIA brand icons for the use cases

2.3 The SYNTHIA brand images – a selection

2.4 The SYNTHIA infographics – a selection

2.5 The SYNTHIA brand book

In addition, the communication team has developed the first version of the SYNTHIA brand book. A brand book is essential for ensuring consistency, recognition, and professionalism in all the SYNTHIA communication and outreach activities. It gives a quick overview of how SYNTHIA presents itself visually right from the start enabling recognizability and impact during the life cycle of the project. The communication team will make an effort, considering the multiple stakeholders involved in the SYNTHIA community, that all presentations and materials are aligned with SYNTHIA's identity. Annex 1 of D10.2 presents edition 1.0 of the SYNTHIA brand book.

As SYNTHIA evolves, the communication will grow and the developed house style will provide strong foundation for scaling communication efforts without deviating from the core identity.

3 The project website

Developing a website for a newly established IHI project that is shaping its collaborative framework comes with unique challenges. To ensure a scalable and effective solution, we will design a phased development approach. The URL of the SYNTIA website is www.ih-synthia.eu.

3.1 Phase 0 - Web presence

- Objective: Provide an online presence at the launch of the SYNTIA project, a webpage was published in September 2024 (See annex 2). Annex 2 of D10.2 presents screenshots of the web page.

3.2 Phase 1 - Website

- Objective: Offer an online compact central hub to systematically increase the visibility of SYNTIA, and subsequently also the SYNTIA activities and expert teams. Enable stakeholders and interested audiences to be informed about the project approach, objectives, outcomes, news and events.
- Homepage: Will be visually attractive, user friendly and to-the-point, designed to grab the user's attention and guide them effectively to any other section on the website to keep them engaged.

- The launch of the SYNTHIA website phase 1 is scheduled for mid March 2025
- Sitemap:

3.3 Phase 2 – Website

- Objective: Offer an online central hub to systematically increase the visibility of SYNTHIA, and subsequently also the SYNTIA activities and expert teams. Enable stakeholders and interested audiences to be informed about the project approach, objectives, outcomes, news and events.
- To add to sitemap: Key activities and/or Key offerings and/or SYNTHIA Platform and/or SD Applications.
- Concepts for phase 2 will be developed based upon user experience and upon suggestions from SYNTHIA partners and external stakeholders. Execution of new features and new interactive style content will also be dependent on budget possibilities.
- Realization of phase 2 of the website is scheduled for spring 2026.

3.4 Platforms and channels integrated in the SYNTHIA website

- The Zenodo tool will be the online platform for listing SYNTHIA deliverables, publications or other research outputs developed by SYNTHIA Partners and work teams, regardless of size or format. Zenodo is the open repository for EU-funded research outputs from Horizon Europe Programmes.
- The SYNTHIA LinkedIn page will echo the news items and other website content. The SYNTHIA LinkedIn page will also generate traffic to the website.
- Video and podcast content listed at the SYNTHIA YouTube and Podbean channels will be disclosed at the SYNTHIA website.

3.5 Content development

Content for the SYNTHIA project website will be created with a strategic, audience-focused approach. By leveraging expertise from the SYNTHIA partners and their key team members, the content will be both informative and engaging. Mechanisms will be put in place to ensure accuracy, relevance, and clarity. Additionally, content will be continuously optimized based on user feedback and performance metrics, ensuring it effectively supports the visibility, dissemination, and outreach goals of the project. The SYNTHIA web management will be the responsibility of the WP10 communication team.

The content for SYNTHIA will include a range of formats designed to engage and inform different target audiences. Examples of content items:

- Text content such as project updates, themed articles and research findings with attractive images and graphics.
- Multimedia content such as videos interviews and podcasts.

The variety of content will ensure that the project resonates across different platforms, fostering a dynamic and ongoing engagement with the target audiences.

4 Conclusions

The purpose of deliverable D10.2– Project Identity and Website is to provide a comprehensive overview of the visual identity developed for the project, ensuring a consistent and professional appearance throughout its duration. By establishing a cohesive and recognizable brand from the start, this visual identity lays a strong foundation for ongoing communications, engagement, dissemination and exploitation activities. It will help to build a lasting presence for the SYNTHIA project. The project website (www.ih-synthia.eu) will serve as a key communication tool, offering stakeholders easy access to project updates and resources. It will be regularly updated to reflect the SYNTHIA progress, engage its audience, and support the continued sharing of results and achievements throughout its lifecycle.

Annexes

Annex 1 of D10.2 | Edition 1.0 of the SYNTHIA brand book.

SYNTHIA Brand Book

Contact for all SYNTHIA communications
and dissemination, including artwork:

Ellen [P.B.] de Waal
e.dewaal@matical.com | +31 654 711703

Primary Logo

Primary Logo

“

Our logo blends a DNA-like strand with digital dots, forming a subtle “S” to signify the fusion of real world and synthetic data. The design represents the bridge between the need for comprehensive patient data and the challenges associated with accessing real patient data. With its vibrant colors the logo encapsulates continuity, innovation, future of data and technology.

Primary Logo

*Primary
Logo with tagline*

Vertical

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

*Primary
Logo with tagline*

Horizontal

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Founders logo set

Always use together with the project text and a white background. If there is a dark background, the logo set should be placed on a white stripe at the bottom of the layout, with the stripe's top-right side curving upward.

This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bío, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV.

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Logo rules

Logo rules

Typography & Color

Typography & Colors

Primary

Plus Jakarta Sans

Nam fuga. Et et enimill essitatiis
dolorumet autem fugias alic tem il
idellor ehentur. Quisci bera volupta
vel et. Minullab orporrore magnim.

Secondary

Calibri

Nam fuga. Et et enimill essitatiis
dolorumet autem fugias alic tem
il idellor ehentur. Quisci bera
volupta vel et. Minullab orporrore
magnim.

Brand imagery

Brand imagery

Dark theme

Primary

Diseases

General

Brand imagery

Light theme

Primary

Diseases

General

Brand in action

Brand in action

Mock-ups to give you some idea.

Brand in action

Brand in action

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@IHI_SYNTHIA x.com/IHI_SYNTHIA

www.linkedin.com/company/ihl-synthia

www.youtube.com/@ihl_synthia

www.ihl-synthia.eu

contact@ihl-synthia.eu
(for external communications purposes)

